

Gas chromatography profiles of IR26 molecular and steam distillates. IRRRI, 1988.

transferred to the extract collector, and the apparatus left to equilibrate at room temperature for 24 h.

The extract was then saturated with sodium chloride and extracted 3 times with 2 ml of HPLC grade dichloromethane (DCM) each time. The DCM extract was concentrated to 50 µl and kept at -20 °C until GC analysis.

Fresh IR26 foliage (200 g) also was extracted by the standard steam distillation method. The extract was concentrated, weighed, and diluted to 500 ppm with HPLC grade DCM and kept at -20 °C until GC analysis.

GC analysis was performed on a Varian 3700 GC equipped with a 25 m × 0.25 mm CP-1 column using He as carrier gas at a flow rate of 1 ml/min. Injector and detector temperatures were set at 170 °C and heating to 250 °C, respectively. Oven temperature was programmed from 2 min at 50 °C to 250 °C at 5 °C/min. One µl of extract was used for analysis on the splitless mode.

The figure shows the GC profiles of IR26 molecular distillate and steam distillate. It is clear that molecular distillation gives more signals in the low molecular weight region (early in time); in contrast, steam distillation gives more

signals in the high molecular weight region. These results suggest that the low molecular weight components are either destroyed or are not efficiently recovered under the steam distillate method. □

Drought tolerance

Screening deepwater rice cultivars for drought tolerance under field conditions

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We evaluated 140 deepwater rice accessions for drought tolerance. Seeds

were sown directly on 8 Jul 1987 in three 2.5-m-long rows 20 cm apart. Drought tolerance and drought recovery were scored using the *Standard evaluation system for rice*.

Rainfall during the cropping period was 385 mm, against the average 950-1,000 mm. Drought occurred at different crop stages (see figure).

Entries suffered from drought at the vegetative and reproductive phases. Only 10 entries (see table) flowered and set seed. □

Drought spell during cropping period. Bahraich, U.P., India.

Drought tolerance and recovery score of best^a entries. Bahraich, U.P., India.

Entry	Cross	Drought tolerance	Drought recovery
IET10543	FR13A/CNM539	3	3
IET10544	FR13A/CNM539	3	3
IET10545	FR13A/CNM539	3	3
IET10569	Mahsuri/B11	3	5
IET10584	IET5854/Mansarovar	3	3
IET10585	IET5854/Mansarovar	3	3
IET10595	Janki mutant	3	5
IET10596	Janki mutant	3	5
IET10597	Janki mutant	3	5
IET10603	CNL J3/Cula II//IR13415-9-3	3	3
Madhukar (local check)		5	5

^a All have a phenotypic acceptability score of 5.